

FRENCH PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH A ZOONYM COMPONENT.

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Annotation: In this article, to identify and systematize lexical-semantic, linguoculturological and structural features systems of modern personal names in French. Competence of the anthroponym form, knowledge of a foreign language and knowledge foreign cultural models of personal names is one of the most important conditions the success of the process of intercultural communication. Many questions related to the functioning of personal names have been considered by various disciplines.

Key words: zoonimy, onomastics, semantics, identification, linguoculturology.

Most phraseologists paid primary attention to the special status of phraseological units in the language, their specific categorical properties, and unmodeled syntactic structure. The internal contents of these units remained virtually out of sight. In addition, the task of identifying the special essence of phraseological meaning was solved mainly by comparing the meanings of phraseological units and words.

The bulk of research by foreign linguists, in particular French, was carried out in a diachronic manner. Typical in this regard is the work of P. Guiraud, who is primarily interested in the etymology of the properties of phraseological units, and who sees the main reason for phraseologization in the presence of linguistic or extralinguistic (extralinguistic) archaism in the composition of the phrase.

In this study, we did not abandon the attempt to find out the reasons and origins of the appearance of relevant features of phraseological units. But we tried to transfer the direction of analysis of these units to synchrony and, first of all, to their semantics, as the most significant, essential, emphasizing their national identity and determining their properties in the functional, communicative and connotative planes.

Putting forward the concept of the specificity of the structure of the semantic content of phraseological units, we set ourselves the goal of studying the semantic space of the language, which is revealed by analyzing the semantics of phraseological units with a zoonym component in the French language.

Having chosen French phraseological units containing a zoonym, we could not even foresee that a relatively limited set (only 1500 phraseological units) would appear as an exceptionally multifaceted phenomenon.

We examined the object of study from different angles, and as a result, the study acquired the character of a multidimensional analysis of linguistic material. The work reflects various issues (some of them are debatable in modern science), such as: the formal grammatical organization of phraseological units, the specifics of the semantic structure, functional features, pragmatic meaning, significance in the processes of cognition and objectification of the world.

During the study, we made a number of conclusions.

Firstly, we classify phraseological units with a zoonym component as nominative units as a result of secondary indirect nomination due to the presence in their semantic structure of a subject-conceptual core, which helps to correlate these units with the realities of the surrounding reality.

Secondly, in the structure of phraseological meaning, the dominant component is the connotative component, which explains the unlimited possibilities of phraseological units in the role of expressing emotional and evaluative meanings, relegating the nominative function to the background.

Thirdly, in line with the new broad interpretation, connotation appears as a component of the PU, which contains the most important semantic elements that correlate with certain components of the external structure of the PU, and with its functional purpose, as well as a wide range of ethnocultural information. Phraseologisms are an encyclopedia of knowledge about the French people - a native speaker of French: about unique character traits, habits, views, customs, history, way of life. Thanks to phraseological units, a person penetrates into an unknown national culture and becomes acquainted with the enormous wealth stored in the language being studied.

Fourthly, phraseological units with a zoonym differ from other types of phraseological units of the French language in their stylistic reduction. Distributed primarily in the colloquial-familiar, vernacular and argotic functional registers, they are a means of communication, a way of adding brightness to speech and, to some extent, a speech code for the lower strata of French society and individual professional groups.

Fifthly, from the point of view of expressing the meaning of the overall "good/bad" assessment, the vast majority of phraseological units studied are marked negatively. Moreover, a distinctive feature of this type of phraseological units is the inclusion in the evaluative aspect of their meaning of various private evaluative values (sensory-gustatory, psychological, aesthetic, ethical,

normative), which make it possible to reveal the features of the value scale of French speakers.

Sixth, one of the purposes of phraseological units with an animalistic component as specific nominative-expressive means is to depict a complete, finely differentiated "portrait" of a typical representative of a linguistic community speaking French, and to display his physical, moral, intellectual, and social appearance. From here we conclude that phraseological units with a zoonym are anthropomorphic, that is, they reflect those realities and spheres of life that are closely related to the person himself, his activities, his interests, etc.

Finally, we believe that the specific features of the structure of the meaning of French phraseological units are partly due to the semantics of the key word, which is a zoonym, which influences the formation of phraseological meaning, introducing elements of its semantic content, namely: the semes "a person with the property of an animal", "property animal, inherent in man", "assessment".

As it seems to us as a result of the analysis carried out, the study of phraseological units with a zoonym component would be useful to continue with the involvement of wider linguistic material, perhaps some classes of background vocabulary of the French language or even phraseological corpora of other languages, in order to establish the reasons for the historical, etymological, social the nature of various language processes.

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